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MANAGING ATTRITION AND ESTABLISHING EFFECTIVE RETENTION STRATEGIES– AN EMPIRICAL STUDY OF SELECTED ITES-BPO COMPANIES IN MANGALORE, KARNATAKA

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Abstract

There are very few organizations, where problem of employee attrition is less or controllable. In India, the BPO sector is facing highest rate of attrition is at the junior/ entry level. There are telecom, FMCG and Financial Sector etc. In BPO highest attrition is at the junior / entry level. There are various factors that make an Entry Level BPO Executive to level one BPO and join another. While an employee leaving the individual, it is most often means a career move, economic growth and enhancement of the quality of life .So what is a problem for one in the value chain may be an opportunity for the other BPO. Attrition rate is a burning issue for BPO HR professional as they face tremendous problems like losing the talents and knowledge, cost related to training, recruitment act. A creative thinking is required about the talent management challenge in the BPO sector. An industry- specific innovative technique has to be built by being clear about the current economy trend. The talent' management practice has to remain volatile and flexi to incorporate change as and when demanded. This research paper is an endeavor to find out the reasons of high attrition rate in BPO sector. The sample size has been taken to be BPO employees (including entry, junior and middle levels). To achieve the objective of the study a Descriptive Research was conducted using Likert Scale and a structured questionnaire was circulated to around 600 respondents. The data was collected from the respondents to know their views regarding the issues, problem and the quality of work life in BPOS. Primary sources comprise of interview and direct responses collected through questionnaire.

Keywords: Attrition, ITES-BPO, Global markets, Retention, Strategies

INTRODUCTION

The last decade saw an upheaval in the growth and development of the Indian economy, which was accompanied by the revolution in the technological front and a radical change in the way businesses were done. Instead of being the jack-of all- trades, the smart organizations have now redefined the way of working and now aim at being the master of their core business. Outsourcing the non-core processes in order to concentrate on the core ones is how the

companies prefer to work now. BPO has become the obvious strategic choice of the phenomenal lifestyles seem to flash the mind in a jiffy. That's just the start. One reads it again, contemplates over it, dives into the unveiled afflictions, and gives it a second thought and companies looking at the visible profits of cost reduction while improving the quality of service, increasing shareholder value etc. With the whirlpool of opportunities the Indian Business Process Outsourcing sector seems to be on a happy ride. It has emerged rapidly, and its exports have grown from \$565 million in 2000 to about \$7.3 billion in 2005. With the boat steaming ahead in the global markets, India has already become the most privileged destination. Hence such an eternal inventory of opportunities simply showcases a phenomenon, which is no less than the renaissance for our Indian markets.

Attrition in BPOs has terrible effects on the organization. The high attrition costs increases the costs to the organization considerably. They have to combat the amount of disruption due to unplanned exits. The more the people leave an organization, the more it is a drain on the company's resources like recruitment expenses, training and orientation resources and the time. The high attrition rate also affects the productivity of the organization. Therefore, it is extremely important to curb attrition not only for an individual firm but also for the industry as a whole. Many researchers have worked enormously on the IT & BPO sector, citing its challenges, issues, and opportunities in and around employee performance, employee satisfaction, employee turnover etc.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Grossman and Helpman's (2005: 135) statement, "We live in an age of outsourcing," clearly designates that outsourcing has now become an acknowledged, accepted and established business strategy. One of the most familiar forms of outsourcing is business process outsourcing BPO, i.e., transferring the operational ownership of one or more of the firm's business processes to an external supplier that, in turn, administers the processes according to some predefined metrics (Ghosh and Scott, 2005; Stone, 2004). BPO or Business Process Outsourcing thus refers to the rearrangement of entire business functions to some other service providers, primarily in low cost locations. The service provider may be either self-owned or a third party. This

relocation or transferring of business processes to an external provider is essentially to accomplish increased shareholder value.

Some of the general services provided by the BPOs are Receivables and Payables, Inventory Management, Order Processing, Cash flow Analysis, Reconciliation, Data Entry, Payroll Processing, QuickBooks Accounting, Financial Statement Preparation and Accounting Services. Some of the web based services include live online sales and order entry, E-commerce transaction support, live online enquiry handling, Web design/development.

Reduced international trade barriers and improved telecommunication and IT capability over the past decade has led to a situation where organizations across the world are increasingly interlinked with each other. This has resulted in intense global competition, challenging business managers across the world to find ways to reduce the cost of conducting business and accessing global resources in meeting the need of global markets. In such a context, the reorganization of business models to leverage benefits of outsourcing and focus on core competencies has become a key strategy pursued by large corporations across the world. BPO service-providers are expected to provide a wide spectrum of benefits to their customers, ranging from having greater expertise in the outsourced processes, lower costs achieved through economies of scale, scalability and the ability to absorb cyclicity of loads.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

It is clear from the review of BPO research that solutions are required to some specific problems of practical importance in the field of escalating attrition and retention in BPOs. The broad objective of this paper is to identify the root causes of attrition and retention in BPOs, analyzing the level of employee motivation, satisfaction and involvement, generate a model for maximizing sustenance of employees in the organization and come up with concrete recommendations, which will eventually be valuable to the organizations to retain their employees for a long term. The specific objectives of this paper are:

- To identify and rank the factors of attrition in BPOs based on accumulative literature review and secondary data.

- To develop a regression model for escalating the stay of employees in BPOs and give recommendations for the same.
- To assess the existing level of employee motivation and validate the model by studying the impact of recommendations on a small patch.

BPO IN INDIA

Currently the sector employs approximately 2,45,100 people and another 94,500 jobs are expected to be added in the current financial year. There are over 400 ITES-BPO companies operating in the Indian market, including captive units (of both MNCs and Indian companies) and third-party services providers.

In terms of markets, the US continues to be the main consumer of India's ITES-BPO services (with a 66% share of the market), followed by Western Europe (including the UK), which accounted for 20% of export revenues. In terms of functional service offerings, Customer Care and Support services contributed approximately 34% of the industry's revenues with the other leading service lines including Finance (with a contribution of 22%), Administration (13%) and Content Development (19%). The global financial services vertical remained the largest user of Indian ITESBPO services, followed by telecom, healthcare and airline segments. Captive units continued to dominate the ITESBPO industry, accounting for over 65 percent of the value of the work off shored to India.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Both Quantitative & Qualitative methodologies were used in research. Due to the time and geographic limitations a sample survey was conducted. Simple Random Sampling method was used. The sample size has been taken to be around 600 BPO employees (including entry, junior and middle levels) from 60 Domestic and Global BPOs pertaining to Mumbai .To test the validity and veracity of the structure of the questionnaire and to find out whether the purpose would be fulfilled a pilot study was conducted where data was collected from 150 BPO employees including executives of all the level to find opinion of the employees on the causes of attrition in a BPO. The pilot survey was followed in a detailed survey of around 600 BPO employees. Along with survey interviews were also conducted on personal basis.

PRIMARY DATA ANALYSIS

A questionnaire was intricately designed to tap the factors responsible for attrition, the factors that are expected to be present in a specific job for retention. The instrument was divided into 4 parts. The first part gathered information about the personal profile of the respondents which included their age, gender, education, marital status, and tenure. Part II consisted of questions about their reasons for change or probable change in their jobs. Part III aimed at knowing what according to the respondents is important for their sustenance in an organization. And last of all, Part IV was about their overall perception of the work which included their level of satisfaction, level of motivation, level of involvement and level of life interest and work compatibility.

SECONDARY DATA ANALYSIS

In order to gain a deeper understanding about the phenomenon of high attrition, and identification of the factors behind it, a lot of literature on BPO, particularly what got published during 2004 and 2015 was studied in detail. Major causal factors for high attrition in Indian BPO industry identified in this study were based on qualitative research using secondary data. These were compared with causal factors for attrition identified through personal interview with a number of BPO employees in the Mangalore City.

Table No. 1: Summary of Ranks

Causal Agents / Factors	Score (on 1) (Rank)
Higher Salary Expectation	0.7 (Rank-II)
Lack of Security	0.3 (Rank-V)
Lack of Social Interaction	0.3 (Rank-V)
Monotonous Work	0.8 (Rank-I)
Unusual Working Hours	0.7 (Rank-II)
Pressure to perform on Metrics	0.5 (Rank-IV)
Low Perceived Value	0.8 (Rank-I)
Disillusioned Employees	0.6 (Rank-III)
Stress and Burnout	0.5 (Rank-IV)
Lack of Motivation	0.5 (Rank-IV)

There was a close similarity between the two results, authenticating the qualitative research on causal agents for attrition identified in this study. The study ranked low perceived value and monotonous work as number one factor attrition. Rank two was shared by high salary expectation and unusual working hours. Next factor was disillusioned employees; rank four was

shared by stress and burnout, pressure to perform on metrics, and lack of motivation. Finally rank five was jointly shared by lack of security and social interaction.

OBSERVATIONS AND RESEARCH FINDINGS

The survey measured employee attrition based on 7 parameters. These parameters are Autonomy, Recognition, Belonging Job Satisfaction, progress & development work environment & self-efficacy. Respondents were asked to rate these factors on the five- point scale (Likert Scale) where 5 stand for strongly agree and 1 stands strongly disagree. Research findings under these parameters are as follows-

Autonomy

Autonomy is the degree to which one can make significant decisions without the consent of others. BPO employees enjoy very little operational autonomy. As e move up in the hierarchy the level of autonomy is improving. Especially Entry and Junior levels executives were of the opinion that they perform their duties under strict supervision, they have very less freedom to restructure their job schedule.

Out of 308 Entry level Executives, only 1% entry level executives strongly agree and on the other side 14% strongly disagree that they enjoy autonomy in their work proceedings. 7% enjoy autonomy in there in comparison to 46% disagreeing. 33% are in the neutral category. Out of 144 Junior Level Executive only 6% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 13% strongly disagree that they enjoy autonomy in their work proceedings. 19% respondents agree disagreeing. 35% are in the neutral category. The study reveals out of 606 BPO employees, 3% respondent strongly agree and 11% strongly disagree regarding autonomy. 14% BPO employees agree that BPO wherein 36% employees totally disagree to this .35% respondents were undecided about autonomy.

Recognition

Recognition involves being valued by others in the company. An individuals' contribution to the organization is noticed and appreciated. According to the survey findings all BPOs have an effective employee is slightly more as we move up in hierarchy. BPO employee

were of the opinion that they get timely feedback from their team leaders, which motivates them to perform better. Different BPOs have different criterion/ ways for employee recognition. In one of the BPO surveyed one of the criterion was serving a customer without being asked to help by a supervisor, each employee, who meets the stand criteria, receive a thank you note, hand-written by the supervisor.

Out of 309 Entry Level Executives only 2% respondent strongly agree and on the other side 6% strongly disagree that they have enough recognition in their BPOs. 22% Entry level executives agree that recognition is there in comparison to 32% disagrees. 37% are undecided. Out of 145 Junior Level Executives only 8% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 7% strongly disagree that they have recognition. 23% Junior Level Executives agree that recognition is there in comparison to 26% disagreeing. 36% are in the neutral category. Out of 155 Middle Level Executives only 8% respondents strongly agree and on the other side only 5 % strongly disagree that they get required recognition. 30% Middle Level Executives agree recognition is there in comparison to 21% disagreeing. 36% Middle Level executives are in the neutral category. In context of Recognition out of 608 BPO employees 5% respondent strongly agree and 6% respondents strongly disagree. 24% BPO employees agree that they enjoy recognition in their BPO wherein 28% employees totally disagree to these 37% respondents were in neutral category.

Job Satisfaction

Job satisfaction is a collection of feelings that an individual holds towards his/her job. Job satisfaction represents an attitude rather than a behavior. In this research study the job satisfaction is one of the most critical parameter. The level of job satisfaction is higher among middle and upper level BPO employees in comparison to entry and junior level executives. BPOs are making considerable efforts to retain middle level executives. They get pay raises, praise, recognition, increased promotional opportunities and so forth. Few attempts are being made by the BPOs to retain entry-level executives. Study reveals drop in employee job satisfaction in BPOs is due to heavier employee workloads, tighter deadlines and another contributing factor is employee have less control over their work. Entry level executive have high expectations about attractive job opportunities in BPO industry enhances their decision to leave the current job. Entry-level executive are in hot demand and often these fresh out of

colleges graduates hop from one job to another, till they can hop no more. With each jump, their package generally goes up by as much as 20%.

According to survey findings out of 308 Entry-Level Executives only 1 % respondent strongly agree and on the other side 10% strongly disagree on this parameter.13% Entry-level Executives agree that they are satisfied with their jobs in comparison to 44% disagree. 31% are undecided about their job satisfaction. Out of 144 junior Level Executives only 6% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 9% strongly disagree.19% junior level executives agree in comparison to 30% disagree. 36% are in the neutral category. Out of 155 Middle Level Executives only 7% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 5% strongly disagree regarding job satisfaction. 27% middle Level Executives agree job satisfaction is there in comparison to 22% disagreeing. 39% Middle Level Executives are in the neutral category.

In context of job satisfaction out of 607 BPO employees 4% respondent strongly agree and 9% respondents strongly disagree.18% BPO employees agree that they are satisfied with their jobs wherein 35% employees totally disagree to this. 34% respondents were in neutral category.

Belongingness

Belonging refers to the being part of the organization, it is a feeling of pride that I belong to this organization. Belonging is closely related to recognition. Belongingness is the human need to be an accepted member of a group. Belongingness is an attitude of recognizing yourself with your BPO. According to survey findings belongingness is good in BPO employees but currently entry level executives are being badly affected by poaching practices which are prevailing in BPO industry.

Out of 309 Entry Level executives only 5% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 8% strongly disagree on this parameter. 13% Entry-Level Executives agree that they belong to their BPO in comparison to 31% disagree. 43% are undecided about their belongingness. Out of 145 Junior Level Executives only 8% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 7% strongly disagree. 22% Junior Level Executives agree in comparison to 26% disagreeing. 37% are in the neutral category. Out of Middle Level executives only 6% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 5% strongly disagree regarding belongingness. 25% Middle Level

Executives agree belongingness is there in comparison to 25% disagreeing. 39% Middle Level Executives are in the neutral category. In context of Belongingness out of 608 BPO employees 6% respondent strongly agree and 7% respondents strongly disagree. 18% BPO employees agree that they belong to their BPO wherein 28% employees totally disagree to this 41% Middle Level Executives agree progress & development is there in comparison to 29% disagreeing. 40% Middle Level Executives were in the neutral category.

Progress & Development

Study reveals that program & development is also a vital parameter. Progress and development refers to the “internal rewards available from the organization challenge and accomplishment” External rewards are usually given in the form of salary and benefits also include promotion, rank and status. According to the study the entry level and junior level executives are not aware of their career path in the BPO. They don’t know after what time they will be entitled to become Team Leaders or Supervisor etc. At entry level job is quite monotonous, scope for skill variety and task identity is low. Many domestic BPOs do not provide sufficient Training & development program to their executives. They lack in transparent performance appraisal system in comparison to global BPOs. AS per survey findings Entry-level executives were not at all satisfied on this parameter.

Out of 309 Entry Level executives only 2% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 13% strongly disagree on this parameter of progress & development. 5% Entry –Level executives agree that they got enough opportunities for progress & development in comparison to 41% disagreeing. 38% are undecided about their career paths in BPOs. Out of 145 Junior Level Executive only 5% respondents strongly disagree. 23% Junior Level Executives agree in comparison to 28% disagree. 34% were in the natural category. Out of 154 Middle Level Executives only 3% respondents strongly agree. And on the other side 6% strongly disagree regarding 23% Junior level executives agree in comparison to 28% disagree regarding progress & development. 21% Middle Level Executives agree progress & development is there in comparison to 29% disagreeing. 40% Middle level Executives were in the neutral category. In context of progress & development out of 608 BPO employees 3% respondent strongly agree and 11% respondents strongly disagree. 14% BPO employees agree that their BPO is giving them

wanted career path wherein 35% employees totally disagree to this. 38% respondents were undecided about this variable.

Work Environment

Hygiene, working condition, free breakfast, lunch dinner, pick-up& drops, regular family get-together and other recreation activities are the common facilities provided by all the domestic and global BPOs.

According to survey findings out of 307 Entry- Level Executives 7% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 5% strongly disagree. 23% Entry-Level Executives agree that they are satisfied with their work environment in comparison to 24% disagree. 40% are undecided about their BPO work Environment. Out of 144 Junior Level Executives only 12% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 5% strongly disagree. 26% junior level executives agree in comparison to 21% disagree. 36% are in the neutral category. Out of 153 Middle Level Executives only 9% respondents strongly agree and on the other side only 4% strongly disagree regarding BPO work environment. 32% middle level executives agree BPO work environment is fairly good in comparison to 18% disagree. 37% middle level executives are in the undecided category. In context of Work Environment out of 604 BPO employees 9% respondent strongly agree and 5% respondents strongly disagree. 26% BPO employees agree that work environment of their BPO is good wherein 22% employees totally disagree to this. 38% respondents were undecided about this variable.

Self- efficacy

Self efficacy is a quality, wherein the employees are self motivated to achieve their targets. According to research findings generally BPO employees are self motivated to achieve their targets. They are being treated with dignity and respect. In relation to adherence to system specification while communicating with clients BPO employees do not compromise and maintains the quality of their work.

According to the research study out of 306 Entry-Level Executives 6% respondent strongly agree and on the other side 7% strongly disagree regarding their self- Effectivity in BPO.

23% Entry-level executives agree that they are effective in comparison to 28% disagree. 36% are undecided about their self- efficacy.

Out of 144 Junior Level Executives only 11% respondents strongly agree and on the other side 6% strongly disagree. 26% junior level executives agree in comparison to 23% disagree. 35% are undecided about their self- efficacy.

Out of 151 Middle Level Executives only 9% respondents strongly agree and on the other side only 3% strongly disagree regarding self- effectively. 30 % middle level executives agree in comparison to 19% disagree. 38% middle level executives are in the undecided category.

In context of Self efficacy out of 601 BPO employees 8% respondent strongly agree and 6% respondents strongly disagree. 26% BPO to achieve their targets wherein 24% employees totally disagree to this. 36% respondents were undecided about this variable.

Overall mean for the Autonomy is 2.6. Overall mean for the Recognition is 2.9, Overall mean for the Job satisfaction and Belongingness is 2.7, overall mean for the Progress & Development is 2.6 and Overall mean for the Work Environment and Self-Effectively is 3.1.

According to survey findings on all seven parameters BPOs need to improve, this will help to reduce employee attrition. As the research findings reveal that the concentration of attrition is mainly at entry and junior level. BPOs are required to frame new acquisition and retention strategies especially for these employees.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

Both the hypothesis has been proved positive and validated by secondary data. The key organizational Hr issue being faced today by all the companies is attrition. Researcher is of the opinion working on these parameters; Autonomy, recognition, belonging, Job satisfaction, Progress & Development, Work Environment and self- efficacy, will definitely help BPOs to better understand their employees' need. Good understanding of employees' need will result into forming a better retention strategy.

The study reveals that the lack of career growth, dissatisfactory compensation and poor quality of supervision are the most important reasons that contribute to employee attrition. Due to monotonous nature of job, entry and junior level of employees change their jobs frequently and the average period is one to two years. Condition of attrition varies from small to big domestic to global BPOs. Entry and Junior level executives are needed to be empowered. More recreational

activities are required to make entry and junior level executives' jobs stress free. Career plan should be well employees at all the level. The BPOs are needed to frame competitive compensation strategies. BPOs are required to build better employee engagement activities rigorous trainings for employees at all the levels, stress free culture which will boost employee belongingness towards their BPOs. Regular exit interviews, sound appraisal system clubbed with employee growth plans are the right ways to control the attrition rate.

Retention strategy forms an important part of recruitment strategy. Hr plays a critical in forming retention strategy of a BPO. HRM is a strategic approach to the acquisition, development, motivation and retention of the organization's human resources. Survey findings reveals that BPOs are directly focusing on the retention aspect to curb the problem of attrition, which can't achieved until they focus on the preceding HRM functions as acquisition, development motivation. BPOs are needed to frame the right kind of recruitment strategy (recruiting the right kind of a person with right mindset at the right place at the right time). Which should be followed by transparent employees' developmental plans for all the levels of BPO employees. Developing the potential of employees, providing the right kind of culture will result into self-motivated employees. Some of the respondents revealed biased facts due to the fear that their employment status will be affected.

The researcher has made the following suggestions based on her findings and observations.

1. Pay attention to the aspect of attrition at the recruitment stage itself. Recruiting the right person at the right place at right time is essential for every BPO. Every BPO should have clear recruitment philosophy that should be well linked with right employee development and motivational strategies. Right people can be selected through competency screening and using psychometric test.
2. An employee's work must be communicated to him clearly and thoroughly. Make employees clear on performance linked incentives and other benefits. Keep these promises, later.
3. A formal and informal, vertical and horizontal communication channel is required for the relaxation of employees.

4. Understand and solve employees' problems through proper counseling and guidance through awareness program.
5. Employees at all the levels must be rewarded, recognized and appreciated on a regular basis.
6. BPOs should form a work-life balance policy which will have an impact on retaining the employees.
7. Competency Model integrated with HR processes like selection & recruitments, training, performance appraisal and potential appraisal will be beneficial for all the BPOs.
8. Focus on retaining intellectual capital even when employees leave. Think of appropriate mechanisms and build organizational memories and knowledge systems to retain talent and intellectual capital.
9. More importance to be given to recreational activities s mind refreshing sessions, laughing club etc.
10. Grievances should be redresses then and there to keep the employer- employee relationship intact.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Organizations should have a proactive retention strategy which helps in reducing employee turnover. Retention plan strategies should be different for different level of employees, because their roles are different; their needs are different; what motivates them are different and what makes them leave are also different. Based on the study it has been seen that dimensions of satisfaction and motivate are significantly different for employees on the basis of age, gender, marital status and education. Then, the regression model revealed that intrinsic motivation and involvement factors, as well as age and education level contribute to the sustenance of employees in the organization. Thus based on the findings, it can be said if the employees are motivated and involved in the work they can be retained.

The ease of retention would depend on their degree of motivation and involvement. It is desirable to plan employee retention strategy by an organization, which should cover following aspects:

- Reciprocity is the key. Employees are investors in the company and expect a return on investment. The return can be in the form of recognition, empowerment and authority.
- Retention must be part of the organization’s DNA. Successful organizations have woven retention and engagement deeply into their structure.
- Loyalty is never given. Loyalty must be earned; even satisfied employees sometimes leave. Therefore, develop sense of loyalty among the employees.
- Organizations must be seen as employers of choice. One has to compete on compensation and benefits, but win on culture, learning and development.
- Stars include more than just the top 10% - or 1%! Stars are people at any level who sustain in the organization and bring value to it.

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